

A Study of Effect of Watching Cartoons on the Behavior of School Going Children

Dr. Irfan I. Shaikh

Assistant Professor,

Iqra College of Education, Jalgaon.

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to find out the effect of watching cartoons on the behavior of the school going children. POGO, Cartoon Network, Nick and Disney channels are the most favorite cartoon channels for children. All these channels are 24 hours channels, so children spend most of their leisure time in front of it. It not only attracts the children through its contents but also inculcates some positive and negative habits in them. One of the main factors which influence the children while watching cartoons is violence. Now a day's violence is a vital part of most of the cartoon programs. Children are attracted by violent contents of such programs. They not only imitate their favorite cartoon characters like Chhota Bheem, Ninja Hattori, Spiderman, and Ben Ten but even force their parents to buy the same costumes or accessories as displayed by different cartoon characters. This study aimed to demonstrate the gender-specific impact of violence-oriented cartoons on school going children, and to identify the behaviors demonstrating this influence.

Keywords: Cartoons, Children behavior, Violence.

Introduction:

Today television (TV) is one of the important parts of our modern society. Children spend their much more time in watching TV than participating in any other activity. Cartoons and animated films were once the favorite program of viewers of the different age groups in the society. These cartoons and films were enjoyed but all most every person, from different walks of life on their television sets and theatres. In the beginning when the animated movies and cartoons started their journey, these programs contained both humor and entertainment for all ages. Cartoons, however, now lacked their cross-generational appeal and converted into "kids' stuff" (Kellogg, 1992)¹. Cartoon is not a precise term now a day as it is applied to multifaceted graphic form. It is the most entertaining source for kids as they developed a strong affiliation and attachment with it (Kemnitz, 1973)².

Now a day, cartoon watching is the most favorite hobby of children in their leisure time, so they like to watch the cartoons on television rather than to do any physical activity. Cartoon watching affects the attitude and behavior of kids i.e., their liking and disliking, way of talking, and behaving with other children. It also has a strong effect on their language and the way of their dressing and eating. POGO, Cartoon Network, Nick and Disney channels are the most favorite cartoon channels for children. All these channels are 24 hours channels, so children spend most of their leisure time in front of it. It not only attracts the children through its contents but also inculcates some positive and negative habits in them. One of the main factors which influence the children while watching cartoons is violence. Now a day's

violence is a vital part of most of the cartoon programs. Children are attracted by violent contents of such programs. They not only imitate their favorite cartoon characters like Chhota Bheem, Ninja Hattori, Spiderman, and Ben Ten but even force their parents to buy the same costumes or accessories as displayed by different cartoon characters.

Review of Literature:

An experimental study to assess the effects of TV cartoon network on the aggressive behavior of school going children with the objective to identify the impact on children viewing cartoon network. Data are collected from 192 (96 boys and 96 girls) school going children .the study showed that children spend more time on watching cartoon and acquiring much information not only about type of cartoon characters but also they are familiar with the action ,dress and name of almost all major cartoon characters, it was also observed from the empirical findings that watching cartoons on the television screen has tremendously increased aggressive behavior among children liked fighting more than female children .it was further observed that significant majority of the overall, male and female children often fought inside and outside homes, but the male fought somewhat more with other children than the female children.³

An experimental study was conducted to find out the effectiveness of interactive programmes among children from 2-5years of age with the objective to analyze the interactive content of children's television like Chutti, Disney, and Pogo and to find out the effectiveness of these programs among children from 2-5 years of age. Children while watching, do they discuss the programme after watching, are they enjoy and also parents of 2-5years old children's, teachers of primary school or class and experts in child psychology is been interviewed. The children were showed pre-recorded interactive programme from these channels, the researcher also conducted in depth interview from parents, teachers, and experts in the field related to children to find the need for interactive programme content in children.⁴

An experimental study was conducted to assess the perceived impact of cartoon films on children with the objective of this research was to find the impact of cartoon films on thinking, feeling and behavior of children, and to study the perception of the parents about the same on their children. The sample size contained 120 individuals- 60 children, 30 male, 30 female parents selected randomly from the population of Indore. The findings stated that the children had favorable perception towards cartoon films (thinking, feeling) while non-favorable towards cartoon films (behavior). The perception of male and female children did not differ but perception of male children was significantly higher than that of female children towards behavior. Parents had favorable perception towards cartoon films (thinking, feeling) and non-favorable towards behavior.⁵

An experimental study was conducted to assess the effect of television on social behavior of teenagers with the objective to assess the perception of teenager's, parents of teenagers with respect to impact of television on their social behavior and also to compare the mean perception score of male and female teenagers and parents of teenagers with respect to impact of television on their children's social behavior. The sample size of research was

containing 300 individuals, which included 100 teenagers and their 100 father and 100 mothers. The research was survey in nature. The data was collected by a questionnaire. The findings stated that there was significant impact of television on the social behavior of teenagers with respect to their perception and the perception of their parents and there was no significant difference between the mean perception score of male and female teenager's and their parents with respect to impact of television of their teenagers' social behavior.⁶

Clara and Marian (1980) studied the impact of TV cartoons on children free play behavior. Same children were observed both by researchers and the kindergarten teachers. Sixty-five children and their teachers (n=18) were studied. Every child was individually asked following questions. (1) Which programs do you like most on television? (2) Which cartoon programs do you like the most? (3) Name your favorite cartoon characters? (4) What are the reasons of your liking for these characters? After observing the free play activities (recess/outdoor play activities) of kids, their teachers were asked the following questions. What is your clear evidence from classroom that children have effects of cartoons on them? Do you know about children's favorite programs? The results of the study have shown that cartoons were the most favorite program among the children on television. Children like those cartoons which are broadcasted on weekday afternoon.⁷

Teachers believed that cartoon viewing have a strong impact on "in-class" behavior of children. Children often demonstrate television-related behaviors in the classroom. Research on the violence shown in television programs and video games is clear cut evidence that violent contents will increase aggressive and violent behavior of youngsters in both short-term and long-term context (Anderson, 2003).⁸

Title: A Study of Effect of Watching Cartoons on the Behavior of School Going Children.

Objectives:

- 1) To find out the difference in the duration of watching cartoons among children, based on gender.
- 2) To find out the difference among children's favorite cartoon programme.
- 3) To find out the difference in the level of effect on children by cartoons, based on gender.
- 4) To find out the difference in the way children imitate cartoon characters, based on gender.
- 5) To find out the difference, based on gender, in terms of children's buying items associated with their favorite cartoon characters, such as journals, books, wrappers, bags, erasers, costumes, etc.

Hypotheses:

- 1) There is no significance difference in the duration of watching cartoons among children, based on gender.
- 2) There is no significance difference among children's favorite cartoon programme.
- 3) There is no significance difference in the level of effect on children by cartoons, based on gender.

- 4) There is no significance difference in the way children imitate cartoon characters, based on gender.
- 5) There is no significance difference based on gender, in terms of children's buying items associated with their favorite cartoon characters, such as journals, books, wrappers, bags, erasers, costumes, etc.

Methodology:

The methodology used in this study was survey research. The school going children of the age group 6-10 years (i.e., from Std. 1st to 5th), from different public and private primary schools of Jalgaon City were selected through Simple Random Sampling. A sample of 300 children having television set and cable in their homes was selected. A questionnaire was used for data collection, using face-to-face interviews with the students which occurred during visits to primary schools. In order to remove any ambiguity, they were entertained one by one so that they might not confuse and can easily respond to questions.

Sample:

A sample of 300 children from different public and private primary schools of Jalgaon City having television set and cable in their homes was selected.

Tools used:

A questionnaire developed by researchers, following a literature review was used for data collection.

Statistical Tools:

A non-parametric test of association- “Chi-square test” was used by the researcher for the analysis and interpretation of data.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

Hypothesis -1:

For testing the hypothesis-1, the chi-square test of association was used. The result is shown in Table-1 below.

Daily Duration of watching cartoons (hours)	Female n(%)	Male n(%)	Total n(%)
< 1	104(71.2)	102(66.2)	206(68.7)
2 to 3	37(25.3)	41(26.6)	78(26.0)
3 to 4	4(2.7)	10(6.5)	14(4.7)
> 4	1(0.7)	1(0.6)	2(0.7)
Total	146(48.7)	154(51.3)	300(100)

$X^2 = 11.8563$

Table-1: Children’s daily time spent on watching cartoon by gender.

From the above table, the table value of X^2 for degree of freedom = 3 at $p = 0.001$ level of significance is 16.266. The calculated $X^2 = 11.8563$ is smaller than table value therefore, the hypothesis-1 is accepted and we conclude that there is no significant difference was found between gender and children's daily durations of watching cartoons. It was identified that 71.2% of female and 66.2% of male children watched cartoons at most for one hour in a day, when comparing the daily duration of TV viewing, according to gender. Therefore, it appeared that these female children watched cartoons for longer periods than male children.

Chart-1: Children's daily time spent on watching cartoon by gender.

Hypothesis -2:

For testing the hypothesis-2, the chi-square test of association was used. The result is shown in Table-2 below.

Favorite Cartoon Group	Female n(%)	Male n(%)	Total n(%)
Group A- (Violence Oriented)	44(30.1)	128(83.1)	172(57.3)
Group B- (Educational and Emotion Based)	102(69.9)	26(16.9)	128(42.7)
Total	146(48.7)	154(51.3)	300(100)
$X^2 = 86.01$			

Table-2: Children's favorite cartoon group by gender.

From the above table, the table value of X^2 for degree of freedom = 1 at $p = 0.01$ level of significance is 6.635. The calculated $X^2 = 86.01$ is much higher than table value therefore, the hypothesis-2 is rejected and we conclude that a statistically significant difference was

identified between children's favorite cartoon types and gender. It was identified that, 30.1% of female and 83.1% of male children liked "Group A" (cartoons containing violence and demonstrating power), while 69.9% of female and 16.9% of male children liked the "Group B" (educational, didactic and emotion-based cartoons).

Chart-2: Children's favorite cartoon group by gender.

Hypothesis -3:

For testing the hypothesis-3, the chi-square test of association was used. The result is shown in Table-3 below.

Most Impactful Feature	Female n(%)	Male n(%)	Total n(%)
Characters' behavior (Scenes of Fighting)	8(5.5)	32(20.8)	40(13.3)
Characters' extraordinary actions	37(25.3)	46(29.9)	84(28.0)
Characters' speeches	15(10.3)	14(9.1)	29(9.7)
Story	24(16.4)	12(7.8)	36(12.0)
Music	15(10.3)	8(5.2)	23(7.7)
I am not influenced	47(32.2)	42(27.3)	88(29.3)
Total	146(48.7)	154(51.3)	300(100)

$X^2 = 21.624$

Table- 3: Most impactful feature of cartoon watched by gender.

From the above table, the table value of X^2 for degree of freedom = 5 at $p = 0.05$ level of significance is 11.070. The calculated $X^2 = 21.624$ is much higher than table value therefore, the hypothesis-3 is rejected and we conclude that a statistically significant difference was found between the most impactful features of the cartoons children watch and gender. It was noted that, 5.5% of female and 20.8% of male children were influenced by the behaviors of cartoon characters: 25.3% of female and 29.9% of male children were influenced by the extraordinary behaviors of the characters. A smaller number of female and male children (10.3% and 9.1%, respectively) were influenced by the speech of the characters. The theme of the cartoons influenced 16.4% of female and 7.8% of male children, while the music in the cartoons influenced 10.3% of female and 5.2% of male children.

Chart- 3: Most impactful feature of cartoon watched by gender.

Hypothesis -4:

For testing the hypothesis-4, the chi-square test of association was used. The result is shown in Table-4 below.

Imitation of Cartoon characters	Female n(%)	Male n(%)	Total n(%)
Yes	13(8.9)	14(9.1)	27(9.0)
No	90(61.6)	71(46.1)	161(53.7)
Sometimes	43(29.5)	69(44.8)	112(37.3)
Total	146(48.7)	154(51.3)	300(100)
$X^2 = 8.107$			

Table-4: Children's degree of imitation of cartoon characters watched, by gender.

From the above table, the table value of X^2 for degree of freedom = 2 at $p = 0.05$ level of significance is 5.991. The calculated $X^2 = 8.107$ is much higher than table value therefore,

the hypothesis-4 is rejected and we conclude that a statistically significant difference was found between children's degrees of imitation of the cartoon characters that they watch and gender, with boys imitating characters more often than girls (53.9% and 38.4%, respectively). When children's degrees of imitation of the cartoon characters that they watch was compared across gender, it was observed that 53.9% of male and 38.4% of female children imitated cartoon characters, by their answers of "Yes" or "Sometimes".

Chart-4: Children's degree of imitation of cartoon characters watched, by gender.

Hypothesis -5:

For testing the hypothesis-5, the chi-square test of association was used. The result is shown in Table-5 below.

Purchasing of items related to favorite Cartoon characters	Female n(%)	Male n(%)	Total n(%)
Yes	61(41.8)	54(35.1)	115(38.3)
No	28(19.2)	27(17.5)	55(18.3)
Sometimes	57(39.0)	73(47.4)	130(43.3)
Total	146(48.7)	154(51.3)	300(100)
$X^2 = 1.96$			

Table-5: Purchasing of items related to favorite Cartoon characters, by gender.

From the above table, the table value of X^2 for degree of freedom = 2 at $p = 0.05$ level of significance is 5.991. The calculated $X^2 = 1.96$ is smaller than table value therefore, the hypothesis-5 is accepted and we conclude that no significant difference could be found between children's purchase of stationery items associated with their favorite cartoon characters and gender and it was noted that 82.5% of male and 80.8% of female children bought stationery items associated with cartoon characters (e.g., journals, books, wrappers, bags, erasers, costume, etc.) either "Sometimes" or "Very often". Of the children who

indicated they did not buy these stationery items, 50.9% were female, while 49.1 % were male.

Chart-5: Purchasing of items related to favorite Cartoon characters, by gender.

Conclusion:

- 1) It was determined in the study that male and female children's durations of watching cartoons are almost identical to each other. Therefore, a significant difference was not found between the durations of watching cartoons based on gender.
- 2) In the study a significant difference was determined among children's favorite cartoon groups: male children liked more violence-oriented cartoons in which power was exhibited, while female children liked educational, emotional and didactic cartoons much more.
- 3) According to the findings of the study a significant difference was observed in terms of the amount of influenced perceived from the cartoons, based on gender: male children were influenced by the behaviors and extraordinary actions of cartoon characters, whereas female children were influenced by the speeches of characters, and the topic of and music in the cartoons.
- 4) A significant difference was determined in respect to children's conditions of imitating the actions of cartoon characters according to gender, and it was discovered that male children imitated the actions of cartoon characters much more.
- 5) In the study no statistically significant difference was found in children's buying of the stationery items associated with their favorite cartoon characters and gender.
- 6) According to these results, children should watch violence-oriented cartoons under the control of teachers or families. Cartoons should be analyzed and the disadvantages and harmful effects of violence-oriented behaviors in them should be emphasized.

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